
The Role of Stem Education in Advancing Women's Empowerment and Leadership in Satara District

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Introduction:

Highest participation in STEM field is related to development of region. STEM deals with Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics field. In this emerging 4th revolution era, engagement in STEM field enhance status of individual, sustainable development, inclusive growth and social well-being. Hence STEM education become prerequisite in this era. However in India, women underrepresented in this field. Their participation is also in STEM workforce as compared to male. STEM education is crucial key indicator according to SDG 4 (to ensure equitable quality education and promote lifelong opportunities for all) and SDG 5 (to achieve gender equality and empower women and girls) for achieving goal of sustainable development 2030. According to World Bank report (2018), Women choosing STEM courses has been increasing, but less likely enter into STEM careers or STEM workforce and exit these careers earlier than male. There is need of equal access, equal opportunities for women increasing their contribution in STEM workforce. UNESCO is giving special attention to this issue through research, policy and capacity-building work to promote the empowerment of girls and women through education (www.unesco.org).

According to Pew Research center, some of the highest-earning STEM

occupations such as computer science and engineering have the lowest percentage of women workers. Only around 21% of engineering majors are women, 19% of computer and information science majors are women. 80% of the healthcare workforce are women, but only 21% of health executives and board members are women and only about a third of doctors (www.aauv.org). STEM education enhance critical thinking skills, problem solving capabilities, creativity, innovation capacity of females in fast changing modern economic system.

Study Region:

Satara District locates at the Western limit of the Deccan plateau with hilly reliefs in southern of Maharashtra state. Extreme Western part of the district falls under Sahyadri ranges. The satara District extends between 17° 05' and 18°11' north latitudes and 73°33' and 74°54' East longitudes. There are four distinct river basins in the district that are basins of Krishna, Nira, Yerla and Man. In the Western part of the district, climate is cool and healthy as compared to eastern part. The Western part gets high rainfall. The temperature is high in the plains than on the hills. Medium black to deep black soil, light soils are locally known as malran or murummal, laterite soils are found in district. According to 2011 census, the District has population of 30,03,741

which constitute 2,433,363 rural population and 570,378 urban population. The sex ratio of the District indicates 988 females per 1000 males which is higher as compared to State (929).

Objectives:

1. To study female's status in STEM education in Satara District.

Results and Discussion:

Importance of STEM Education for Females:

Women's Empowerment:

Females equipped with STEM knowledge and skill can solve real world problem. STEM education has power empowering women thorough enhancing their socio-economic status.

Provide Career Opportunities in huge quantity:

Fastest growing worldwide industries are STEM education oriented where females can't enter without acquiring STEM related knowledge, skill and technology. Hence it provide huge career opportunities. According to Pew Research

Leadership:

Table No. 1 Number of Institutions Affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

Sr. No.	Type of Colleges	Total	Permanent	Temporary
1.	Arts, Science, Commerce	147	111	36
2.	Engineering Including Architecture	42	7	35
3.	Management	17	00	17
4.	Pharmacy	19	3	16

Source: www.unishivaji.ac.in

Women are participating in leadership through STEM. Eg. Tessy Thomas is known as the missie lady. She was the project leader for the Agni-IV and Agni-V missile in defence research and development organization. (Dr. Javed Ahmed).

According above table, most of colleges are Arts, Science and Commerce Colleges affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur as compared to other faculties. It is

center, a typical STEM worker earns two-thirds more than those employed in other fields. It help in increasing economic status of women individually.

Closing the Gender Gap:

Literacy rate of women is increasing but women are still underrepresented in STEM field specially in engineering. Hence increased percentage of STEM educated women can bridging the gender gap.

Social Impact:

Women with STEM can contributes in social reformation, social development, closing the gender biasness, destruction of hazardous social traditions and taboos.

Motivate Future Generations:

Successive women in STEM education and careers become role model for other women. It is helpful for enhancing female's confidence to choose STEM oriented education, career and job.

Individual High Socio-economic Status:

STEM helps in increasing socio-economic status for women and high socio-economic status of women is crucial for development of nation and society.

noticeable that permanent colleges are more among Arts, Science and Commerce Colleges. On the contrast, data of temporary colleges shows highest number belongs engineering, management and pharmacy. Hence, it has impact on presentation of females in STEM field especially in engineering including architecture and pharmacy.

Table No. 2 Faculty and District Wise Affiliated Colleges

College Type	Kolhapur			Sangli			Satara		
	Granted	Aided	Non-Aided	Granted	Aided	Non-Aided	Granted	Aided	Non-Aided
Arts, Commerce, Science	1	50	16	0	36	17	0	35	17
Engineering and Technology	0	0	16	0	1	9	1	0	9
Architecture	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	2
Pharmacy	0	0	6	0	0	5	1	0	7

Source: www.unishivaji.ac.in

Above table indicates that there is only one Arts, Commerce and Science government college in Kolhapur District where as other districts have not. However Satara district has 1 granted Engineering and Technology College and 1 granted Pharmacy college. The highest no. of aided arts, commerce and science colleges are present in Kolhapur district and lowest in Satara district. The highest number of non-aided engineering and technology colleges seen in Kolhapur District (16) and lowest in

Satara and Sangli district i.e. 9 district. Non aided Pharmacy colleges are also high in number in Satara District (7) as compared to other districts and lowest in Sangli district (5). Total no. of Arts, Commerce and Science colleges and Engineering and technology colleges are less in quantity in Satara district as compared to Kolhapur district. This table explored that traditional streams of education are high in number in all three districts. It affects presentation of females in STEM education.

Table No. 3 Women's Colleges in Satara

Sr. No.	Tahsils	College Type	Frequency
1.	Satara	Arts and Commerce	1
2.	Karad	Arts, Commerec and Science	2
3.	Wai	Arts and Commerce	1

Source: District, [Socio-Economic Abstract 2018, Satara District.](#)

As per above table, In Satara district 4 colleges are women's colleges. Among them 2 are in Karad, 1 in Satara and I in Wai tahsil. These colleges are found in cities. Unfortunately, no one is related STEM field. These colleges belongs to traditional streams of education. Hence it could be say that it

has impact on women choice to select field. They have tend towards available field in this region. Women's colleges positively affects mindset of parents and female students. However no one women's college related to STEM is found in rural area.

Table No. 4 Category wise Students Admitted for Science and Technology in 2017-2018 in Satara District

Sr. No.	Category	Male (%)	Female (%)
1.	SC	7.75	8.04
2.	ST	0.70	0.50
3.	NT	9.87	8.90
4.	OBC	17.05	17.50
5.	OPEN	64.63	65.06
6.	Total	40.47	37.78

Source: www.unishivaji.ac.in

Data presented in above table indicates that female's contribution in Engineering and Technology faculty is low than male peers in all social categories except in open category. Presentation of females belongs to ST category (0.50) is

very low as compared to other categories. Admission of males (40.47%) is higher than females (37.78%) in this field. Admission of females of backward classes for Engineering and Technology presents very low proportion as compared to Open category.

Table No. 5 Admitted Students in Engineering and Technology by Sex for Years in Satara District

Sr. No.	Year	Male (%)	Female (%)
1.	2012-2013	22.31	11.02
2.	2013-2014	24.26	11.36
3.	2014-2015	23.16	13.25
4.	2015-2016	25.91	12.93
5.	2016-2017	25.07	12.50
6.	2017-2018	22.48	11.65

Source: www.unishivaji.ac.in

Above table represents that admission of female students from 2012 to 2018 years is very less than their counterpart. It is not more than 14%. Highest female students are admitted in year 2014-2015 (13.25%). Again from next year, admission of them decreased up to 2017-2018. In 2017-2018, it declined up to 11.65% which is lowest among last 5 years.

Conclusion:

Female's percentage is much less in the field of Engineering and Technology in Satara district which presents grim situation of women. Even basic right of education is denied to females. So it is difficult to women to reach at the leading positions in science, technology, engineering and mathematics. With the emergence of new technologies, there are various occupational opportunities to women in STEM field such as in automation, robotics, and artificial intelligence. However inadequate knowledge and skill of these technologies, women are underrepresented in STEM related workplaces. It is assumed that STEM fields are masculine and these are not suitable for women. Society underestimate girls' math

ability without testing their performance. General mindset of society is that males are superior than females in STEM field. There is need to change this mindset by developing echo system within schools and colleges by involving all stakeholders such as parents, teachers, administrations, governments and societies. Most of girls do not continue their studies after marriage especially in rural area and if they continue the studies, they usually preferred for humanities and social sciences. Male dominant culture in these fields are not supported or attracted to women and also women in minorities.

Role models also plays important role to change mindset and encouraging females. There are fewer role models in these field in world and negrofy in Satara district. There are limited examples of female scientists and engineers. Due to family constituents, most of women cannot tend to these field. Underrepresentation of female in STEM education, career and workforce have negative impact on gender equality as well as economic growth and sustainable development. STEM education to women also helps breaking gender

stereotypes, gender inequalities and other social expectations that limit female's options, access, opportunities and possibilities.

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